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Relation between 4f-magnetism and the low-temperature magnetocaloric effect in multiferroic hexagonal manganites

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The magnetocaloric effect enables magnetic refrigeration and plays an important role for cooling at cryogenic temperatures, which is essential for emergent technologies such as hydrogen liquefaction and quantum computing. Here, we study the origin of the low-temperature magnetocaloric effect in multiferroic hexagonal manganites. By conducting direct adiabatic temperature measurements in pulsed magnetic fields exceeding 20 T on different $RMnO_3$ systems with varying magnetic 4f-moments (i.e., $R = Y, Ho, Er,$ and Tm), we demonstrate significant magnetic-field-driven reversible temperature changes, ΔT_{ad} . Our data show that the effect is predominantly driven by the rare-earth magnetism, scaling with the effective magnetic moment of the R atom. The largest reversible temperature change is observed in $HoMnO_3$ with ΔT_{ad} of up to 20.1 K, whereas the effect is largely suppressed in $YMnO_3$. Our findings demonstrate the importance of the 4f-magnetism for the magnetocaloric effect in hexagonal manganites, which is expected to be relevant for other magnetic oxide systems and their optimization for refrigeration applications at cryogenic temperature.

Cryogenic refrigeration is essential for numerous advanced technologies, ranging from magnetic resonance imaging and particle accelerators for high-energy physics to quantum computing. Furthermore, the ongoing energy transition, with hydrogen gas as a green energy vector, has renewed the interest in cryogenic refrigeration¹, particularly for developing energy-efficient hydrogen gas liquefiers that can efficiently reach the required temperatures below 21.1 K. As an alternative to conventional compression-based cooling methods—which become increasingly inefficient and costly at these temperatures²—caloric cooling has emerged as a promising technique, leveraging field-induced order-disorder transitions under adiabatic conditions. Models predict that cooling efficiencies of up to 60%^{3–5} can be reached utilizing caloric materials for hydrogen liquefaction, while experimental prototypes integrate various materials functional over the whole temperature regime with fields produced by high-temperature superconducting magnets or superconducting solenoids^{6–9}.

A key parameter in this context is the adiabatic temperature change, i.e., energy change without heat transfer, induced by the applied external stimulus. Adiabatic temperature changes from electric¹⁰ or elastic¹¹ order decrease towards cryogenic temperatures and face fatigue challenges. Thus,

recent research has focused on magnetic materials¹², particularly binary and ternary intermetallic compounds. Examples include rare-earth nickelates¹³, aluminides¹⁴, and Laves phases¹⁵, which show suitable magnetic-field-induced phase transitions in the cryogenic temperature regime and large adiabatic temperature changes. Also non-metals, such as rare-earth borides, show a promising cooling performance¹⁶. Rare-earth oxides are interesting for magnetocaloric cooling applications because of their complex magnetism. A range of different effects arise, for instance, interaction of coexisting magnetic 4f- and 3d-moments, unusual frustrated states^{17,18}, long-range modulated spin textures¹⁹, and anisotropic magnetic behavior²⁰, provides new degrees of freedom for material design²¹. In comparison, little is known about the relation between 4f-magnetism of the rare-earth atoms and the resulting magnetocaloric response at cryogenic temperatures.

The rare-earth hexagonal manganites, $RMnO_3$ ($R = Sc, Y, In,$ or $Dy-Lu$), have been investigated intensively with respect to their magnetism and multiferroic properties^{22–28}, and their magnetic phase diagrams at cryogenic temperature are well-understood^{29–31}. Because of this, the hexagonal $RMnO_3$ family is an ideal model system for the study of the influence of the rare earth ion on magnetocaloric effect in rare-earth

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oxides. In the $RMnO_3$ systems, antiferromagnetic ordering of the Mn^{3+} 3d-moments occurs at $T_N^{Mn^{3+}} \lesssim 120$ K, whereas the R^{3+} 4f-moments exhibit spontaneous long-range order at $T_N^{R^{3+}} \lesssim 10$ K. The magnetocaloric effect in hexagonal rare-earth manganites has already been studied at room-temperature^{32,33} and various studies have reported promising magnetocaloric properties in the cryogenic temperature regime^{34–40}. The research primarily focused on magnetically anisotropic single crystals, which allow for caloric cooling under a constant magnetic field, demonstrating the potential of $RMnO_3$ systems.

Here, we measure adiabatic temperature changes at cryogenic temperature for selected polycrystalline hexagonal manganites with varying magnetic 4f-moments (i.e., $HoMnO_3$, $ErMnO_3$, $TmMnO_3$, and $YMnO_3$). Specific heat measurements show that our polycrystals exhibit the established material-specific sequences of magnetic phase transitions. Direct adiabatic temperature change measurements under pulsed magnetic fields up to 22.3 T verify a pronounced magnetocaloric response. We find substantial adiabatic temperature changes up to $\Delta T_{ad} = 20.1$ K in $HoMnO_3$ and less pronounced effects in $ErMnO_3$ and $TmMnO_3$, which we attribute to their smaller magnetic 4f-moments. The latter is corroborated by the suppression of adiabatic temperature changes in $YMnO_3$, demonstrating that the magnetocaloric effect in hexagonal rare-earth manganites at cryogenic temperatures is predominantly driven by the magnetic order of the rare-earth sublattice. Notably, we identify a direct correlation between the effective magnetic moment of the rare-earth ion and the magnetocaloric response, establishing an engineering parameter for optimizing the magnetocaloric performance of hexagonal manganites and other magnetic oxide systems.

Results

Crystallographic and microstructural characterization

We begin our analysis by characterizing the crystal structure of our polycrystalline samples. Corresponding X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) data are displayed in Fig. 1a, showing that all samples exhibit $P6_3cm$ space group symmetry as expected for hexagonal manganites. Only in the case of $TmMnO_3$, minor secondary phases are observed as indicated by an asterisk

(*), which we attribute to unreacted starting materials. The lattice parameters extracted from a Pawley fit of the XRD data, along with the calculated unit cell volume, are summarized in Table 1. A clear correlation is observed between the unit cell volume and the size of the rare-earth atom consistent with literature²².

Microstructural analysis conducted via Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Fig. 1b, confirms the high density and polycrystalline nature of the samples. Piezoresponse Force Microscopy (PFM) scans, displayed in Fig. 1c, show the established ferroelectric domain structure composed of vortex- and strain-driven stripe-like domains as discussed elsewhere^{41,42}. The data extends previous investigations on polycrystalline hexagonal $ErMnO_3$ ^{43,44} and $DyMnO_3$ ⁴⁵ to isostructural $HoMnO_3$, $TmMnO_3$, and $YMnO_3$ and confirms that these compounds exhibit the $RMnO_3$ -characteristic structural and ferroelectric properties.

Specific heat

After verifying the crystallographic symmetry and the microstructure of our polycrystalline samples, specific heat measurements are conducted to confirm that the materials display the expected magnetic phase transitions at cryogenic temperatures. The specific heat data over a temperature range from 2 K to 100 K are presented in Fig. 2a–d. The observed decrease in specific heat is an important factor for high adiabatic temperature changes ($\Delta T_{ad} \sim 1/C_p$)⁴⁶, making the materials promising caloric refrigeration candidates in the cryogenic temperature regime. The different anomalies in the $C_p(T)$ -curves can be attributed to magnetic phase transitions associated with the Mn^{3+} and R^{3+} sublattices. Consistent with previous studies on the hexagonal manganites^{47–49}, a peak is observed in the specific heat data obtained during cooling below 100 K as indicated by the dashed lines. This peak occurs at the Néel temperature, $T_N^{Mn^{3+}}$, indicating the onset of antiferromagnetic ordering of the magnetic 3d-moments of the Mn^{3+} ions, forming frustrated triangular spin arrangements in the ab -plane as discussed, e.g., in refs. 28 and 50. The respective transition temperatures are summarized in Table 1, showing a good agreement with the previously reported transition temperatures:

Fig. 1 | Crystal- and microstructure characterization of polycrystalline hexagonal manganites. **a** XRD diffraction data of polycrystalline pellets. A Pawley fit (black line) is fitted to the experimental data, with the difference displayed in red. Quality parameters of the Pawley fits are provided in Table 1. The data verifies the hexagonal target phase, space group $P6_3cm$. A minor presence of secondary phases can be

identified in the diffraction pattern of $TmMnO_3$, as indicated by an asterisk (*). **b** SEM micrograph of the polished surface of the polycrystalline pellets. **c** Vertical component of the PFM response of an area featuring several grains. The boundary between the grains is displayed by a dashed white line.

Table 1 | Crystallographic characterization and magnetic transition temperatures

Composition	Ionic radius or R^{3+} (Å)	a (Å)	c (Å)	V (Å ³)	R_{wp} (%)	GoF	$T_N^{Mn^{3+}}$ (K)	$T_N^{R^{3+}}$ (K)
HoMnO ₃	0.901	6.140(0)	11.415(4)	372.7	11.5	2.7	74	5
ErMnO ₃	0.890	6.115(2)	11.408(1)	369.5	10.6	3.1	79	4
TmMnO ₃	0.880	6.089(0)	11.383(8)	365.5	10.7	2.9	81	10
YMnO ₃	0.900	6.146(0)	11.401(8)	373.0	15.8	3.3	73	-

Unit cell parameters a and c of the $P6_3cm$ space group, along with the resulting unit cell volume, V , are extracted from the XRD data shown in Fig. 1a) using Pawley fits. The quality of the fit, quantified by the weighted profile R -factor (R_{wp}) and the goodness of fit (GoF), are provided. TmMnO₃, the material with the smallest ionic radius, has the smallest unit cell volume. The unit cell volume increases with increasing ionic radius. The ordering temperatures related to the Mn³⁺ and R³⁺ ions, extracted from specific heat data (Fig. 2a–d), are displayed.

Fig. 2 | Specific heat and entropy data of polycrystalline hexagonal manganites. Temperature-dependent specific heat (cooling cycle only) measurements on (a) HoMnO₃, (b) ErMnO₃, (c) TmMnO₃, and (d) YMnO₃ under magnetic fields of 0 T, 2 T, 5 T, and 9 T. Dashed vertical lines display the ordering temperature of the manganese sublattice, $T_N^{Mn^{3+}}$, the reorientation of the magnetic moment of the

manganese, $T_N^{Mn^{3+}}$, and the ordering of the rare-earth sublattice, $T_N^{R^{3+}}$. The entropy change derived from the specific heat data under different magnetic fields, according to Eq. 1, is displayed in (e–h). An enlarged view of the temperature-dependent specific heat data in the 0–40 K range is provided in Fig. S1.

~76 K for HoMnO₃²², ~79 K for ErMnO₃²², ~84 K for TmMnO₃²⁹ and 72 K for YMnO₃⁴⁹. As the temperature is further reduced, we observe another transition in HoMnO₃ at $T_{SR}^{Ho^{3+}} = 36$ K, which originates from a spin reorientation (SR) of the magnetic 3d-moments¹⁷. Anomalies in the specific heat data below 10 K are associated with spontaneous long-range ordering of the magnetic 4f-moments on the R³⁺ sites; we find the lowest transition temperature for Er³⁺ ($T_N^{Er^{3+}} = 4$ K) and the highest for Tm³⁺ ($T_N^{Tm^{3+}} = 10$ K) (Table 1), which is in reasonable agreement with literature data^{27,28}. Details on the ordering mechanism on the rare-earth ions are provided in refs. 29,51, and 52. Note that Y³⁺ has no magnetic 4f-moment and, hence, does not exhibit an additional magnetic phase transition below 10 K. In summary, the specific heat data confirms that the polycrystals synthesized for this work exhibit the established sequence of magnetic phase transitions, which originate from the onset of spontaneous long-range antiferromagnetic ordering of the magnetic moments on the Mn³⁺ and R³⁺ sites.

We next move towards specific heat data recorded under applied magnetic fields up to 9 T. In agreement with previous measurements⁴⁹, we find that the specific heat of YMnO₃ is independent of the applied magnetic field (Fig. 2d). In contrast, HoMnO₃, ErMnO₃ and TmMnO₃ show a pronounced dependency on the applied magnetic field (Fig. 2a–c). For example, with increasing magnetic field, the $T_{SR}^{Ho^{3+}}$ transition first becomes broader and then disappears, consistent with previous magnetic-field dependent specific heat studies on single crystalline HoMnO₃²⁸. Our data further confirm that for all investigated compounds the applied magnetic

field stabilizes the order of the magnetic 4f-moments, which is reflected by a field-driven increase of the transition temperature, $T_N^{R^{3+}}$ ²⁹. From the specific heat, C_p , we calculate the temperature-dependent entropy change, $\Delta S_T(T, H)$ ³³, for different magnetic fields, H , by integrating downwards from 120 K to 2 K:

$$\Delta S_T(T, H) = \int_0^T \frac{C_p(T, H) - C_p(T, H = 0)}{T} dT. \quad (1)$$

For each of the applied magnetic fields, the calculated entropy change is plotted as a function of the temperature in Fig. 2e–h. The largest magnetic-field-induced entropy changes are observed around $T_N^{R^{3+}}$, indicating a close relation between the measured changes in entropy and the magnetic order of the rare-earth ions, which we estimate by the effective magnetic moment, μ_{eff} ,

$$\mu_{\text{eff}} = g_j \sqrt{j(j+1)} \mu_B. \quad (2)$$

Here, g_j is the Landé factor, quantifying the relative contribution of orbital and spin angular momentum to the magnetic moment, j is the total angular momentum quantum number, and μ_B is the Bohr magneton. In line with previous calculations linking the entropy change to the effective magnetic moment⁵⁴, our results show that the experimentally determined entropy change scales with the effective magnetic moment of the rare-earth atom, with HoMnO₃ exhibiting the largest entropy change (10.5 J kg⁻¹ K⁻¹)

and the largest effective magnetic moment ($10.6\mu_B$) in the investigated series (Fig. 4). This is further supported by the calculated entropy change for YMnO_3 , which is independent of the applied magnetic field and negligible throughout the entire temperature range investigated (Fig. 2h). To qualitatively show the magnetic-field dependence, we calculate ΔS_T and plot this difference as a function of the magnetic-field strength at $T = 13\text{ K}$ in Fig. 3 (Table 2). Here, a clear trend of the entropy changes can be seen, with ΔS_T being most sensitive to the applied magnetic field in HoMnO_3 , followed by ErMnO_3 and TmMnO_3 .

Adiabatic temperature changes

We next directly measure adiabatic temperature changes, ΔT_{ad} , in pulsed fields up to 22.3 T (Fig. 5). For comparison, we also determined ΔT_{ad} indirectly from specific heat data, following the methodology outlined in ref. 55, for a field of 5 T. The indirectly determined values agree with the direct measurements, both in terms of absolute magnitude and temperature dependence. Interestingly, the results reveal that the adiabatic temperature change in YMnO_3 is largely suppressed compared to HoMnO_3 , ErMnO_3 , and TmMnO_3 . The absence of a pronounced adiabatic temperature change in YMnO_3 , together with the trend observed for HoMnO_3 , ErMnO_3 , and TmMnO_3 , leads us to the conclusion that the magnetic 3d-moments of the Mn^{3+} sublattice do not play an important role within the investigated magnetic field (22.3 T) and temperature range (10–100 K).

This behavior at cryogenic temperature is fundamentally different from the magnetocaloric response previously discussed for rare-earth manganites at room temperature. In particular, for orthorhombic

manganites, such as Ca and Sr doped LaMnO_3 , emergent magnetocaloric effects were attributed to the Mn^{3+} sublattice^{32,33}. In contrast, in the cryogenic regime, we find a scaling of the magnetocaloric response in hexagonal manganites that strongly depends on the R^{3+} ion. The maximum adiabatic temperature change for HoMnO_3 , ErMnO_3 , and TmMnO_3 occurs around $T_N^{R^{3+}}$. Furthermore, our direct measurements reveal a direct correlation between the magnetism of the R^{3+} ion on the A-site and the magnetocaloric response (Table 2). For HoMnO_3 , which has the largest magnetic 4f-moment, the largest magnetocaloric effect is measured with maximum adiabatic temperature changes, ΔT_{ad} , of 5.2 K (5.0 T), 12.6 K (10.8 T), and 20.1 K (22.3 T).

Figure 6 shows the influence of magnetic field pulses up to 10.8 T (rise time: $\sim 17\text{ ms}$) on the adiabatic temperature change. This setting corresponds to $\sim 30\text{ Hz}$, which is about one order of magnitude higher than the frequencies used in prototypical devices⁵⁶, demonstrating the reversibility of the observed adiabatic temperature changes of our materials under application-relevant frequencies. We find that the change of the adiabatic temperature change with magnetic field strongly depends on the R^{3+} ion, being highest for Ho^{3+} , followed by Er^{3+} , Tm^{3+} , and Y^{3+} (Fig. 4), consistent with the magnetic-field induced entropy changes displayed in Fig. 3. The data show an almost instantaneous response of the material's adiabatic temperature to the applied magnetic field, despite the relatively low thermal conductivity of hexagonal manganites in the temperature regime of interest ($< 1\text{ W/Km}^{57}$). A possible explanation is the magnetic-field dependence of the thermal conductivity, which was found to vary by up to two orders of magnitude under magnetic fields up to 14 T⁵⁷. Importantly, the data in Fig. 6 shows the absence of pronounced hysteretic behavior, demonstrating that the magnetocaloric effect at cryogenic temperatures in hexagonal manganites is highly reversible, enabling an efficient and consistent performance over repeated thermal cycles in cooling applications⁴⁶.

Conclusions

We investigate the magnetocaloric effect and its origin in rare-earth hexagonal manganites in the cryogenic temperature regime by performing direct adiabatic temperature change measurements on polycrystalline HoMnO_3 , ErMnO_3 , TmMnO_3 , and YMnO_3 under magnetic fields up to 22.3 T. Our results show a direct relation between the adiabatic temperature and the magnetic 4f-moment of the R^{3+} ions, whereas contributions from the Mn^{3+} sublattice were found to be irrelevant in the investigated magnetic field and temperature regime. With this, our study identifies the effective magnetic moment of the rare-earth ion as an engineering parameter for the magnetocaloric response of hexagonal manganites in the cryogenic temperature regime, which is in agreement to previous calculations⁵⁴. Furthermore, the direct measurements of the adiabatic temperature changes presented in this work give robust quantitative results and prove the reversibility of the magnetocaloric effect, which previously was concluded indirectly from magnetic-field-dependent measurements. The largest magnetocaloric effect was observed for HoMnO_3 with ΔT_{ad} up to 20.1 K. Considering all R^{3+} ions that naturally stabilize the hexagonal $P6_3cm$ phase of RMnO_3 , the largest magnetocaloric effect is expected for DyMnO_3 (Dy^{3+} , $4f^9$, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 10.6\mu_B$),

Fig. 3 | Magnetic-field dependence of the entropy change at $T = 13.0\text{ K}$. The dashed lines are a guide to the eye.

Table 2 | Entropy and adiabatic temperature changes

Composition	Electron configuration of R^{3+}	Effective magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) of R^{3+} [μ_B]	$B = 5.0\text{ T}$		$B = 10.8\text{ T}$		$B = 22.3\text{ T}$	
			ΔS_T [$\text{Jkg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$]	ΔT_{ad} [K]	ΔT_{ad} [K]	ΔT_{ad} [K]		
TmMnO_3	[Xe] $4f^{12}$	7.6	2.1	1.9	5.0	8.6		
ErMnO_3	[Xe] $4f^{11}$	9.6	5.5	5.9	11.1	15.1		
HoMnO_3	[Xe] $4f^{10}$	10.6	10.5	5.2	12.6	20.1		

The electron configuration of the R^{3+} , visualized in Fig. 4, is provided. The calculated effective magnetic moment, μ_{eff} for different R^{3+} ions is displayed. The entropy change is calculated from specific heat data (at $T = 13.0\text{ K}$) according to Eq. 1 as displayed in Fig. 2e–h).

whereas an even smaller response than TmMnO_3 is expected for YbMnO_3 (Yb^{3+} , $4f^{13}$, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 4.6 \mu_B$). In contrast, no significant magnetocaloric effect is expected for ScMnO_3 , LuMnO_3 , and InMnO_3 due to the absence of unpaired 4f electrons⁵⁸.

Fig. 4 | Correlation between the effective magnetic moment of the R^{3+} ion in RMnO_3 and the change in entropy and adiabatic temperature under different magnetic fields. The dashed lines are a guide to the eye. The electronic configuration of the R^{3+} ions is provided in the inset. The errors indicate the electrons in the 4f shell, highlighting that a higher number of unpaired electrons leads to a higher magnetocaloric effect.

Our findings show the possibility to systematically tune the magnetocaloric response in the cryogenic regime by modifying the R^{3+} sublattice. This approach is of interest also for other rare-earth oxides, including rare-earth vanadates⁵⁹, indates⁶⁰, chromates⁶¹, ferrites⁶², and scandates⁶³, which are increasingly recognized for their promising magnetocaloric properties at cryogenic temperatures. Finally, the multiferroic nature of hexagonal manganites within the cryogenic regime⁶⁴ provides a rich and so far unexplored playground for the emerging field of multicaloric cooling⁶⁵, where order parameters controlled by different external fields can enhance various aspects of caloric refrigeration.

Methods

Synthesis

The polycrystals of HoMnO_3 , ErMnO_3 , TmMnO_3 , and YMnO_3 are synthesized via a solid-state synthesis approach from raw-oxide materials. For the synthesis, Tm_2O_3 (99.9% purity, AlfaAesar, Haverhill, MA, USA), Ho_2O_3 (99.9% purity, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), Er_2O_3 (99.9% purity, Alfa Aesar), Y_2O_3 (99.9% purity, Alfa Aesar), and Mn_2O_3 (99.0% purity, Alfa Aesar) are utilized. Tm_2O_3 , Ho_2O_3 , Er_2O_3 , and Y_2O_3 are furnace dried at 900 °C, while Mn_2O_3 is dried at 700 °C for a dwell time of 12 h. Stoichiometric amounts of both raw powders are weighed, ball milled for 24 h at 205 rpm, and heat treated at 1100 °C for 12 hrs in air. The powder is pressed uniaxially into cylindrical pellets with a diameter of 10 mm, followed by isostatic compaction under a pressure of 200 MPa. The final densification of the pressed pellet is done at 1400 °C for 12 h. A more detailed description of the synthesis can be found in ref. 43 for the case of ErMnO_3 .

Crystallographic and microstructural characterization

The processed ceramic pellets are investigated by XRD (D8 ADVANCE, Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA), and the respective lattice parameters are determined by Pawley fitting⁶⁶ using Topas. For

Fig. 5 | Adiabatic temperature changes under magnetic fields, plotted as a function of the initial pulse temperature, T_i . The data is displayed for (a) HoMnO_3 , (b) ErMnO_3 , (c) TmMnO_3 , and (d) YMnO_3 . The data points display the adiabatic temperature changes measured directly under applied magnetic field pulses of different field strengths ranging from 5.0 T to 22.3 T; dotted lines are guides to the eye. Adiabatic temperature-changes during field application were extracted at the

specific maximum magnetic field (Fig. S2). The dashed lines are calculated adiabatic temperature changes from the entropy data measured under 5.0 T (Fig. 2), as described in ref. 55. Dashed vertical lines correspond to the respective ordering temperatures determined from specific heat measurements (Fig. 2a–d). The magnetic-field dependence of the adiabatic temperature changes is presented in Fig. S3.

Fig. 6 | Magnetic-field-dependence of the adiabatic temperature change measured at $T_i \approx 13.0$ K of different rare-earth compositions at magnetic fields up to 10.8 T. Exemplary data on ΔT_{ad} as a function of time is shown in Fig. S2.

microstructural characterization, samples are lapped utilizing a 9- μm grained Al_2O_3 water suspension (Logitech, Glasgow, Scotland), followed by a subsequent polishing step utilizing a silica slurry (SF1 Polishing Fluid, Logitech). SEM is performed on a Helios NanoLab DualBeam Focused Ion Beam (Thermo Fischer Scientific, MA, USA) using secondary electrons for imaging. The electron beam has a 5 kV acceleration voltage and a 0.17 nA beam current. PFM is performed using an NT-MDT system (Spectrum Instruments Ltd., Limerick, Ireland) with an electrically conductive tip (Asyelec.01-R2, Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, UK). The PFM measurement is performed at a frequency of 40.14 kHz with a peak-to-peak voltage of 10 V. The vertical deflection of the laser is read out as $R \cdot \cos \Phi$, with amplitude, R , and the phase Φ of the piezoresponse using a lock-in amplifier (SR830, Stanford Research Systems, CA, USA).

Caloric measurements

The heat capacity of the polycrystals is measured as a function of temperature in constant magnetic fields of 0 T, 2 T, 5 T, and 9 T using a Dynacool PPMS system (Quantum Design, San Diego, CA, USA). Adiabatic temperature changes are measured directly at the Dresden High Magnetic Field Laboratory of the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf in pulsed magnetic fields up to 22.3 T between 10 K and 100 K. The time to reach the maximum magnetic field was ~ 17 ms. To realize direct temperature measurements, each sample is cut into two flat rectangular pieces, $\sim 4 \times 2 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$, utilizing a diamond wire saw (Well Diamond Wire Saws SA, Mannheim, Germany) and a differential type-E thermocouple made from 25 μm thin constantan and chromel wires is fixed between these pieces by a small amount of silver epoxy in a sandwich-like structure to measure the adiabatic temperature changes directly. The thermocouples are calibrated and checked using data from the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). The sensitivity of the thermocouples depends on the temperature resulting in uncertainties of ~ 1.0 K at 10 K, 0.4 K at 30 K, and 0.1 K above 50 K. Potential parasitic effects from magnetic field variations are ruled out by tests conducted in magnetic fields up to 10 T. After fixing the samples on the sample holder, the insert is evacuated to a vacuum of 10^{-3} mbar. More details on the direct adiabatic temperature change measurements can be found in ref. 67.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Author contributions

J.S. conceived the study and processed the polycrystalline samples. E.A.C.P. performed the diffraction measurements and analyzed the crystallographic data. R.D. performed the direct adiabatic temperature measurements together with C.S.M. and T.G. I.H. and R.D. carried out the scanning probe measurements. Y.E. and Y.H. conducted the specific heat measurements. R.D. analyzed the data and created the figures under the supervision of J.S. J.S. wrote the manuscript together with D.M. All authors contributed to the discussion of the results and to the final version of the manuscript.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics

This study adheres to ethical research practices, ensuring inclusivity and diversity in its scope and collaboration. The research team consists of members from diverse backgrounds, contributing varied perspectives and expertise. No individual or group was excluded based on ethnicity, gender,

or other characteristics. The work complies with all relevant ethical guidelines and institutional policies.

Additional information

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